

Bit Analysis: A Visualization System for Bitcoin Wallet Investigation

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KEYWORDS

User-Friendly Interface,
Wallet Summary Visualization,
Transaction Graphs,
Filtering Options,
Export Capabilities.

ABSTRACT

Bitcoin is gaining ever increasing popularity. However, professional skills are required if people want to check bitcoin transaction information from the block chain. As pointed out in a recent study, there is a lack of tools to support effective interactive investigation of bitcoin transactions. Therefore, we present a novel visualization system, BitAnalysis, for interactive bitcoin wallet investigation. The analytical and visualization functions of Bit Analysis are defined and developed by following the advice and requirements of a group of entrepreneurs and regulators of bitcoin-related business.

Bit Analysis provides a rich set of functions and intuitive visual interfaces for the users, such as law-enforcement officers and regulators, to effectively visualize and analyze the transactions of a bitcoin wallet (i.e., a cluster of bitcoin addresses) and its related wallets, to track the flow of bitcoins, and to identify wallet correlation using our novel clustering functions. To achieve these functions, we have designed new visualization techniques for presenting bitcoin transactions information and introduced the connection diagram and bitcoin flow map as new ways of analyzing, tracking and monitoring the trading activities of a cluster of closely related wallets. We also present an extensive user study that validated the effectiveness and usability of Bit Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

AT the first, bitcoin was invented by Satoshi Nakamoto in 2008 as a payment method that people would use to make purchases through bitcoin transactions, which has become a reality. For example,

people routinely purchase daily necessities with bitcoins as a means to fight inflation in Venezuela. With the tremendous increase in adoption of bitcoin for transactions, there is a corresponding increased demand to monitor and analyze bitcoin transactions, either for

investment or for criminal investigation. The goal of the present paper is to meet this demand by developing a complete interactive system for intuitive visualization and effective analysis of bitcoin transactions. Note that a person, also called an entity, can possess multiple bitcoin addresses, like the way a person has multiple bank accounts. To be clear, in this paper, we refer a wallet w to be a collection of addresses clustered by Wallet Explorer [2] as owned by the same entity and a trader of w to be any wallet that have transactions with. Although bitcoin wallets and bank accounts are similar, they are different in terms of anonymity. As centralized institutions, banks know the owner identity of every bank account in the world using fiat currency. When a conventional financial transaction occurs, such as a wire transferring or a credit transferring, the Know-Your-Customer (KYC) principle must be strictly enforced so that customer identities are validated. This allows banks to conveniently monitor and investigate bank accounts, reducing the risk of having transactions with untrustworthy people. In contrast, bitcoin is designed to be pseudonymous. In the world of bitcoin, no centralized institutions exist to check and validate the identities of the owners of bitcoin wallets. Therefore, no one knows the true identity of a bitcoin owner. This anonymity brings about a difficulty for both parties of a bitcoin transaction – We do not know whether we are trading with a dishonest company, a con man or a criminal in money laundry business. So in practice, for exchanging bitcoins with other individuals or institutions or making a purchase using bitcoin, checking the attributes of a bitcoin wallet in question is the only way to minimize the risk of trading with “bad guts”. Indeed, due to the anonymity and decentralization, criminal organizations are naturally interested in using bitcoin for settlement. The last step of a crime is often accomplished by the transaction of money. Hence, governments all over the world find it necessary to monitor and analyse suspicious bitcoin transactions and the associated wallets. Intuitive software tools for wallet investigation are therefore important for regulators. Despite the anonymity of bitcoin ownership, there are certain trading patterns that can be used to characterize the behaviour of the unknown entity. For example, a newly founded company should have only a limited number of transactions, small businesses normally should not have transactions with a large bitcoin volume, and entities

intentionally hiding the origins of their bitcoins are likely involved in illegal activities. Our BitAnalysis system explores these traits for effective analysis in bitcoin transaction investigation. There have been active studies and software systems for bitcoin-related query and examination [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. Among the existing works, there are only two online systems that are commonly used for exploration of individual bitcoin addresses/wallets – Wallet Explorer [2] and Blockchain.info [10]. However, both systems are only for primitive data query as they only display transaction records in a list format without an intuitive visualization or summarization, and support no high-level summary, analysis, or interactions. When using such a system to investigate a bitcoin wallet involved in many transactions, it becomes very onerous to trace all the transactions: One has to keep clicking on the next button to view pages after pages of transactions shown in lists of numerical values. More recently, wallet-based visualizations were studied in [9], [11], [12], [13]. However, these methods cannot demonstrate the complex relationship among trading wallets with intuitive visualizations. As pointed out by a recent review on existing online bitcoin visualization tools [1], there is a stark lack of effective visualization and analysis tools that allow the user to easily and interactively investigate bitcoin transaction data for various potential users. A bitcoin wallet under investigation can be involved in thousands of transactions in a short period of time. It is therefore a challenging task to develop a visualization and analysis system for bitcoin wallet investigation that is capable of visualizing all the involved transactions, related wallets and activities in a clear, ordered, and efficient manner. To understand the requirements for the functions of such an interactive visualization system for bitcoin wallet analysis, we have conducted interviews with numerous bitcoin experts, entrepreneurs in cryptocurrency, and regulators investigating bitcoin-oriented money laundering. Based on these interviews, we summarize the requirements as follows: (1) visually intuitive browsing of wallet summary; (2) efficient analysis of transactions patterns; (3) tracking of bitcoin flows; and (4) continuous monitoring of suspicious transactions. We have designed and developed our Bit Analysis system base on these requirements. The main interface of BitAnalysis is shown in Fig. 1. BitAnalysis facilitates bitcoin wallet

investigation by providing the following functions: (1) Easy browsing and visualization of a wallet summary from different perspectives, such as the top trading wallets, period of peak trading activities, balance variations, etc; (2) Visualization, analyzing and clustering wallets based on transaction patterns; (3) Tracking how bitcoins flow between wallets; and (4) Monitoring interested wallets in real time and alerting the user to new suspicious transactions.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 Bitcoin Analysis: With the wider spread of bitcoin, researchers have a stronger interest in its economic impact, potential risks, and technological limitations. Bitcoin related researches appear across various disciplines. The topics range from bitcoin property [14], anomaly detection [15], [16], [17], [18], regulation [19], [20], privacy analysis [21], [22], to trend prediction [23], [24]. However, most of the existing works on bitcoin analysis focused on the macro characteristics of bitcoin. On the contrary, our system aims at assisting exploration and investigation of specific bitcoin wallets. We also observe that an important category of researches on bitcoin analysis relies on transaction pattern analysis. Moser et al. [17] provided a systematic inquiry on evaluating bitcoin as a money laundering tool and presented outlines of anti-money laundering strategies based on bitcoin transaction information. Reid and Harrigan [25] analyzed the anonymity of bitcoin by investigating bitcoin flow. Ranshous et al. [26] constructed directed hyper-graphs of exchange centered transactions to understand potential money-laundering behavior. Most recently, Wu et al. [27] proposed a bitcoin transaction network analytic method for facilitating Block chain forensic investigation based on an extended safe Petri Net. Our system also provides transaction pattern analysis. But note that the existing works mentioned above mainly focus on the analytical process of network patterns rather than visualization capabilities to facilitate the analysis.

2.2 Bitcoin Visualization: A main category of bitcoin-related visualizations aims at displaying information for demonstration purpose [3], [4], [5], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33]. TxhighWay [28] and TxStreet [31] intend to educate people about the mechanism of bitcoin block chain; Bitbonkers [3], BitTxVis [4], BitLis ten [5], daily block chain [29] and WIZBIT [30] mimic the

real occurrence of bitcoin transactions; Bitnodes [32] estimates the relative size of the bitcoin peer-to-peer network by finding all of its reachable nodes. Meanwhile, bitcoin big bang [33] shows the emergence over time of the largest entities on the Bitcoin block chain, and their interconnectivity. Despite the interesting and vivid visualizations shown, the above works do not provide adequate interactive visualization and analytical functions for analysis purpose. Recently, analysis-oriented visualization becomes an active research direction. Christin et al. [34] investigated Silk Road related data via a comprehensive measurement analysis. Battista et al. [7] and McGinn [8] provided block-level visualizations for anomaly detection. Bistarelli [35] presented to find specific transactions or addresses with customizable filters. Besides, Kondofretal. [36] and Maesaet al. [37] proposed to analyze the overall bitcoin transaction network by measuring the network characteristics and visualize the results. Meanwhile, visualization for analyzing inter exchange behavior has been proposed as well [6]. More recently, Zhong et al. [9] proposed a Silk Viser system to visualize cryptocurrency transaction data from the block chain perspective. Our BitAnalysis are different from the above works from different aspects. SilkRoadTravel [34] only focused on the specific silkroad analysis, but BitAnalysis is design to support custom wallet analysis. BlockChainVis [35] proposed predefined filters to filter out undesired information for transactions visualization while we emphasize on wallet relationship analysis and find out their relevance. Different from block based anomaly detection [7], [8], we rely more on visualizing transaction patterns for analysis. Different from overall block chain visualizations from the macro perspective [36], [37], we aims at bitcoin investigation from the micro perspective. Compared with the exchanges-oriented visualization [6], our BitAnalysis can be applied to analyse wallets not limited to those belonged to exchanges. Though SilkViser [9] also visualized transaction data, it focused on demonstrating transaction data on a block-basis rather than emphasizing the relationship analysis between wallets as our BitAnalysis. In Addition, comparing to the existing wallet-based visualizations [11], [12], BitAnalysis can facilitate wallet analysis from the temporal dimension as well as the relationship dimension, providing more advanced investigations.

2.3 Network Visualization: Network visualization is another related area which has been actively studied. In [38], Her and Boyd used a node link diagram to represent the relation between end-users in online social networks. Wang and Mueller [39] visualized causal networks with path diagrams. Christina et al. [40] adopted a Sankey diagram to visualize dynamic network for data journalists. Besides layout design, researchers also attempted to adopt different technologies to better illustrate a network. Some previous works [41], [42] used edge bundling to simplify a graph. Wang et al. [43] proposed a visual technique to reveal ambiguities. Langevin [44] presented a visual analytical approach to leverage cluster computing by retrieving hierarchical communities from the input data. However, despite of the exits techniques; a net work will be hardly readable with increasing complexity. Therefore, we design a connection diagram to adaptively visualize transaction network and a flow map to clearly show the bitcoin flows between wallets.

2.4 Community Detection: In network analysis, an important topic is community detection. Duchand Arenas[45] took advantages of extremal optimization. Yang et al. [46] made use of node attributes. Pizzuti [47] proposed a genetic-based approach to detect communities in social networks. More recently, community detection for multilayer networks has begun to emerge. Wil son et al. [48] presented a multilayer extraction procedure which could identify densely connected vertex-layer sets in multiplex networks. Li et al. [49] designed a random walk based LART (Locally Adaptive Random Transitions) algorithm to discover communities in a multi-layer network. Clustering is also important for our system to measure wallet similarity. However, the existing clustering strategies cannot be applied directly to bitcoin analysis. Therefore, based on the features of bitcoin, we design specific metrics for bitcoin wallet clustering.

2.5 Visual Analysis of Financial Data although bitcoin is different from fiat currency, research on visual analysis of traditional financial data is also relevant to our work. Anomaly detection is known as financial fraud detection. Fraud investigators have realized that visualizations are very helpful for anomaly detection and various visualization techniques have been developed to help solve the problem. Kirkland et al. [50]

proposed an ADS system on financial anomaly detection by combining the visualization techniques as well as the AI techniques. Based on a set of predefined keywords, Chang et al. [51] presented a Wire Vis system to facilitate banks to discover abnormal wire trans actions. Huang et al. [52] designed a framework of visual analysis for stock market security, with a 3D tree-map to monitor the real time stock market and a node-link network to discover unusual trading pattern. Leite et al. [53] implemented a visual analytic approach (EVA) to help financial institutions conduct fraud transaction detection. Correlative analysis can bring new insights for investors, analysts and financial institutions. Market analyzer [54] presented an interactive system for market and competitor analysis, providing side-by-side comparisons for sales, trends, and growth rates. Malik et al. [55] proposed a visual analytical approach to explore spatial-temporal correlations. Badam et al. [56] presented a system, Time fork, for prediction of multivariate time series data. Note that most traditional financial visual analysis, using macro financial data for macro analysis, are quite different from our work.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

We also observe that an important category of researches on bitcoin analysis relies on transaction pattern analysis. Moser et al. [17] provided a systematic inquiry on evaluating bitcoin as a money laundering tool and presented outlines of anti-money laundering strategies based on bitcoin transaction information. Reid and Harrigan [25] analyzed the anonymity of bitcoin by investigating bitcoin flow. Ranshous et al. [26] constructed directed hyper-graphs of exchange centred transactions to understand potential money-laundering behavior. Most recently, Wu et al. [27] proposed a bitcoin transaction network analytic method for facilitating Block chain forensic investigation based on an extended safe Petri Net. Our system also provides transaction pattern analysis. But note that the existing works mentioned above mainly focus on the analytical process of network patterns rather than visualization capabilities to facilitate the analysis. Our Bit Analysis are different from the above works from different aspects. Silk Road Travel only focused on the specific silk road analysis, but Bit Analysis is design to support custom wallet analysis. Block Chain Vis [35] proposed predefined filters to filter out undesired information for transactions visualization

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4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We present a visualization system, Bit Analysis, for bit coin wallets analysis. This system facilitates efficient wallet preview, new transactions alerting, wallets analysis and bit coin flow tracking. Interactive functions are also provided to assist the wallet investigation procedure. We present a novel connection diagram to demonstrate the connections between wallets as well as design several clustering methods based on bit coin characteristics. These methods can be used to identify wallet similarity and infer wallet ownership. We present a novel flow map to clearly trace and visualize bit coin flows among a cluster of related wallets.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. UML DIAGRAMS

1. Class Diagram

The cornerstone of event-driven data exploration is the class outline. Both broad practical verification of the application's precision and fine-grained demonstration of the model translation into software code rely on its availability. Class graphs are another data visualization option.

The core components, application involvement, and class changes are all represented by comparable classes in the class diagram. Classes with three-participant boxes are referred to be "incorporated into the framework," and each class has three different locations:

- The techniques or actions that the class may use or reject are depicted at the bottom.

Fig 5.1 shows the class diagram

2. USECASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig 5.2 Shows the Use case Diagram

3. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig 5.3 Shows the Sequence Diagram

6. OUTPUT SCREENS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 Admin Page

In above screen shows the all the end users and authorize.

Fig 6.2 Admin Menu

In above screen shows the admin Menu

RID	type	Product_Purchase	amount	nameOrig	oldbalanceOrig	newbalanceOrig	nameDest	type	HCcode
app5044	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	1093.11	C116757915	0.0	0.0	M11954365	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
3yb5Dhc	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	447.07	C528619499	5494.28	933.21	M10073294	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
3u3d4da	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	20479.11	C570456841	993.21	0.0	M511406372	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
gao5Hqk	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	302.68	C526258812	0.0	0.0	M769206846	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
Tb3u2qvy	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	8713.13	C1278197827	0.0	0.0	M675397114	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
juuu4hb	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	10407.53	C1423715209	0.0	0.0	M535149543	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
3y45446	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	768.61	C7192997346	0.0	0.0	M265570846	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
30959p	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	1503.89	C1309659035	0.0	0.0	M477716196	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
wy6z2ac2	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	571.39	C1808482467	0.0	0.0	M182518177	Partial Payment	20200805121010002
3u3d4da	BITCOIN	Home & Kitchen	1548.89	C1060010461	0.0	0.0	M1151255315	Partial Payment	20200805121010002

Fig 6.3 Block Chain Datasets

In above screen shows the all block chain datasets.

Fig 6.4 Payment type Results

In above screen shows the payment type results.

Fig 6.5 User Home Page

In above screen shows the Visualization system for Bitcoin wallet Investigation.

Fig 6.6 View Transaction Type Results

In above screen shows the Transaction type results.

Fig 6.7 Purchased Product Category Type

In above screen shows the Purchased ProductCategory Type results.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented the first visualization system, BitAnalysis, to facilitate investigation of a user-selected wallet. The newly designed connection diagram, similarity metrics and bitcoin flow map greatly help analyze the trading activities of related wallets. Our system has been validated by an extensive user study, which indicates that BitAnalysis is effective for wallet investigation. We hope that our work can inspire more research on bitcoin analysis systems and promote the global legalization of bitcoin.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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